
EFFECT OF INDIRECT TAX REVENUE ON INCOME DISTRIBUTION IN NIGERIA

¹Jacinta Ogochukwu Ebubechukwu and ²Femi Joshua Falope

¹Department of Accountancy, School of Business & Management Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Nekede, Nigeria

²Department of Accountancy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

E-mail: ogo4ebube2010@gmail.com, fj.falope@unizik.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15728657>

Abstract: *This study ascertained the effect of indirect tax revenue on income distribution in Nigeria from 2000 -2023, using stamp duty tax and custom and excise duty tax as the independent variables.*

Ex Post Facto research design was employed by the study. Data were extracted from federal Inland Revenue services and World Bank reports. Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The results revealed that value added tax and custom and excise duty tax significantly affect income redistribution in Nigeria, while stamp duty tax has no significant effect on income redistribution in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that in order to reverse the insignificant effect of stamp duty tax, government should provide the necessary enabling environment that are needed to support both domestic and foreign investment so they can attract more capital gain that will boost taxable income thereby improve in the economic growth of these countries.

Key words: *Stamp duty tax, Custom and excise duty tax and Gini coefficient*

Introduction

The apparent increase in income inequality is due to a number of reasons, including limited employment opportunities, driven by the high concentration of economic opportunity in some areas, crowding out residents of other cities in terms of employment and living conditions. At the same time, the country's high administrative costs, which annoy many people, have also contributed to the increase in inequality, while almost 60 percent of the country's population lives in poverty, the members of parliament and a minority of them have the highest salaries in the country, earning up to \$118,000 per year (Lustig, 2018).

Suna, Metehan and Fadime (2019) noted that taxes are described as indirect if the burden can be shifted from the initial tax payer to others while direct taxes are those whose burden cannot be shifted

from the original payer to others. Redistribution is the use of tax and transfer policies to reduce income inequality; although it does not equalize the rich with the poor, it does raise the consumption capacity of the poor to a more comfortable consumption threshold. Overcoming income inequality requires effective economic policies such as taxation (Lustig, 2017).

Edoni, Okafori and Akhigbodemhe (2020) and Ezu and Okoh (2016) reported that taxation assist in generation of funds that are used to afford social amenities and ensure adequate conditions for general financial well-being, emphasizing the redistributive effect. Nevertheless, taxes can have a negative impact on the purchasing power of individuals and businesses if not managed well (Edo, Okafor & Justice 2020b, 2020a). Meanwhile (Bhartia, 2009) held that the main reason for imposing a tax is to collect revenue for government use, redistribute revenue and control the economy of the country.

The high administrative costs of managing state affairs are at the expense of infrastructure and related investments for economic development and growth. Similarly, rampant corruption and corruption, whether withholding salaries and pensions of civil servants, nepotism or dirtying the hands of policemen, tends to redistribute income from the masses (Ugbede, 2020). Growing income inequality has a negative economic impact, leading to higher poverty rates, rapid declines in real incomes, private sector spending per capita, declines in social services and overall well-being (The Guardian, 2020). Crime is on the rise and the official poverty rate remains high at 46 percent of the population or 62 percent per capita. Graduate unemployment and layoffs are on the rise, a recurring problem due to deteriorating infrastructure and energy shortages in the real economy (Omoniyi, 2017). The atmosphere of insecurity across the national landscape deepens and has created a bad situation and makes the recovery a fantasy, so the government has to deal with these problems and one way is to distribute resources to areas that need them (The Guardian, 2020).

To the best of the researcher's knowledge, none of the prior studies used environmental tax in their studies, besides; there is a limited study in Nigeria that employed GINI coefficient as a proxy for income distribution. This thereby creates variable gaps for this study that determine the effect of indirect tax revenue on income distribution in Nigeria from 2000 to 2023, using GINI coefficient as a proxy for income distribution.

This study is to empirically examine the effect of indirect tax revenue on income distribution in Nigeria from 2000 -2023. The specific objectives are to;

2. Ascertain the effect of stamp duty tax on income distribution in Nigeria
3. Ascertain the effect of custom and excise duty tax on income distribution in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Taxation

Taxation refers to a mandatory levy imposed by the government on individuals and organizations as an avenue of financing its activities. Okonkwo and Chukwu (2019) affirmed that taxation is an ideal

source of government revenue. Taxation also tries to remove disequilibrium in wealth distribution, reduce the consumption of certain products, protect local industries, and control certain areas of the economy (Aondoakaa, Austine & Isaac, 2022).

Tax revenue is the income that is collected by governments through taxation. Taxation is the primary source of government revenue. Revenue may be extracted from sources such as individuals, public enterprises, trade, royalties on natural resources and/or foreign aid (Sitharaman, 2022). Taxation is the primary source of income for the government. The most important revenue receipts for the government, taxes are involuntary fees levied on individuals and corporations to finance government activities. Tax revenue is defined as the revenues collected from taxes on income and profits, social security contributions, taxes levied on goods and services, payroll taxes, taxes on the ownership and transfer of property, and other taxes (Okeke, Mbonu & Amahalu, 2018b). Taxes collected from both direct tax and indirect tax are the government's tax revenue. It includes collections from income tax, corporation tax, customs, wealth tax, tax on land revenue, petroleum profit tax, value added tax, custom and excise duties and so on (Ashiedu, Okafor, Amahalu & Obi, 2022).

An indirect tax is collected by one entity in the supply chain, such as a manufacturer or retailer, and paid to the government. However, the tax is passed onto the consumer by the manufacturer or retailer as part of the purchase price of a good or service. The consumer is ultimately paying the tax by paying more for the product.

Examples of Indirect Taxes are Value Added Tax, Stamp Duties, Custom Duties (taxes on imported and exported goods), Excise Duties (taxes on locally manufactured goods), and environmental taxes (levied on activities that have negative impacts on the environment). It is pertinent to state that VAT happens to be the principal Indirect tax in Nigeria and globally (George-Anokwuru, 2023).

Stamp and Excise Duty Tax

The history of stamp duty has been investigated in a number of ways. Stamp duty was established in 1765 when the British parliament issued the stamp Act, claims Investopedia (2017). American colonists were subject to the tax, which was levied on every printed paper, including licenses, newspapers, ship papers, and legal documents. At the time, money from stamp fees was used to pay for the placement of troops in specific areas of America (Onwuka & Orji, 2021). In their analysis, Besley, Meads, and Surico (2014) noted that stamp duties have a long history as a type of taxation. They were initially used by the United Kingdom in 1694 for transactions involving vellum, parchment, and paper to pay for the war with France. Despite the 1765 Stamp Act's involvement in the drive for U.S. independence, Besley, Meads, and Surico (2014) assert that success saw the expansion of goods subject to stamp duty, with home transactions included by 1808. With a varied rate and band structure based on the nominal value of those transactions, stamp duty is currently levied on land and property transfers. Transfers of shares in publicly traded firms are likewise subject to stamp duties.

The Stamp Duties Act (SDA) was passed in 1939 in order to provide a legal framework for the imposition of duties on executed dutiable instruments, but its application to dutiable instruments in Nigeria was largely downplayed or even ignored by both duty payers and collection agencies, according to Odiambo and Olushola (2018). Only written papers are subject to the Stamp Duties Act, CAP S8, LFN 2004 (as modified), which is governed by the Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS), the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), and the individual State Internal Revenue Services (IRS) (Ofoegbu, Akwu, & Oliver, 2016). Stamp duties were one of the government of Nigeria's underutilized sources of income until recently. Stamp duties would have been one of the main sources of income for the government due to the broad range of dutiable instruments listed in the SDA, such as agreements, contracts, bank deposits, bills of sale, bonds, certificates, deeds, and legal mortgages, as well as the enormous volume of transactions requiring the execution of such dutiable instruments (Edewusi & Ajayi, 2019). The SDA was, however, nearly out of date and out of touch with reality because it wasn't reviewed or revised for several decades.

Custom duties are commodity taxes of imports and exports while excise duties are commodity taxes levied on goods manufactured within the country (Manukaji, 2018). Fasoranti (2013) described import duty as a levy on imports by custom authorities in Nigeria to raise revenue for the government and protect domestic industries from predator competitors abroad. Oladipupo and Ibadin (2015) argued that import duty is generally on the value of goods or on the weight, dimensions or some other criteria that are determined by the government. Sometimes, the government may want to protect certain domestic products from foreign competition. One way of doing so is by imposing import duty, which makes foreign products more expensive, thus keeping the same domestic products more competitive (Ilaboya, 2013). This is usually done as a retaliatory measure in a trade war. It is based on the value of goods called *ad valorem* duty or the weight, dimensions, or other criteria of the item such as its size (Oladipupo & Ibadin, 2015).

Excise taxes are a well-established component of global tax policy. Excise taxes are used to generate government revenue while providing incentives for market participants to consume and produce less harmful products. With proper design and implementation, excise taxes can improve overall well-being and fund public programs to improve market outcomes. Poor implementation of excise tax policy, however, can create an environment in which people are worse off than if no policy had been implemented in the first place (Adam, 2023). An excise, or excise tax, is any duty on manufactured goods that is normally levied at the moment of manufacture for internal consumption rather than at sale. It is therefore a fee that must be paid in order to consume certain products. Historically, excise duty has been referred to as "sin tax" because of the categories of goods they are being levied on, and in a way, was not really a focus for revenue generation by the government. However, due to the recent fall in the price of crude oil, the government has continuously focused on non-oil revenue sources to support the budget and boost economic growth and development.

Income Distribution

The distribution of money from the richest in society to the poorest in the economy is called income redistribution (Awe and Olawumi, 2012). Income distribution is described by Obaretin et al. (2017) as "the unequal distribution of individual, household, and firm income among different actors in the economy."

It is also clear that economic development has a significant impact on the distribution of income. Contrary to popular belief, specific redistributive measures, such as the provision of public services and goods, are now largely seen as growth-enhancing (Madzinova, 2017). Public spending now clearly affects the quantity and quality of growth and growth in turn leads to distribution of income. Not only has that, but the existing distribution of income determined the content of growth of public initiative. Actual studies of the direct relationship between public expenditure and income distribution focus on the impact of specific public expenditure on specific income groups rather than on total income distribution (MartinezVazquez, 2008).

Gini Coefficient

This is a measure of income distribution. It is based on the Lorenz curve. Lorenz curve shows the income and wealth distribution in a graphical form. It was developed by Lorenz (1905) to analyze wealth inequalities of a society in different periods. It shows the percentage of income and wealth held by a certain proportion of the population. The curve reveals the deviation from the line of perfect equality.

Review of Related Studies

Iwegbe and Daddau (2024) ascertained the relationship between Nigerian economic growth and value added tax from 1994 to 2022. Both descriptive statistical methods and simple regression analysis were employed to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics reveal significant fluctuations in these variables, reflecting diverse economic conditions and policy changes. Strong positive correlations were found among GDP, TR, and VAT emerging as a significant predictor of VAT in regression analysis. The study found that economic growth, as captured by GDP, is a crucial driver of VAT revenue, highlighting the importance of policies aimed at stimulating economic growth while considering the broader fiscal context for balanced and sustainable development. Obadiaru, Brian-Kufre, and Ayeni's (2024) ascertained the effect of tax revenue on Nigerian economic growth from 1991 to 2021. Tax information was sourced from the Federal Internal Revenue Service (FIRS) and the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS), while the Nigerian economy was represented using economic data taken from the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) 2021 Statistical Bulletin. Diagnostic tests like the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test for data stability and descriptive statistics for data normalcy were important methodological techniques. E-View version 9 was utilized as the statistical tool for the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach. GDP was shown to be negatively impacted by value-added tax (VAT) and personal income tax (PIT), but positively impacted by corporate income

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 13 Issue 2, April-June 2025

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 8.36

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

tax (CIT) according to the ARDL analysis's findings. Babayanju and Animasaun (2024) studied the relationship between the inheritance tax and wealth redistribution in Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted. The population of the study was the entire staff of Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS) of Nigeria resident in Abuja and is members of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) and Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria (CITN) totalled 549. The regression analysis was employed to test data. The result revealed that inheritance tax significantly affected wealth inequality between the haves and haves-nots in Nigeria. The study further revealed that inheritance tax had statistical significance on illegal acquisition of wealth. Finally, the study found that inheritance tax had a negative and insignificant impact on the productivity of taxpayers. Appah and Iweias (2023) determined the effect of taxes on income inequality in Nigeria from 1980 to 2020. The secondary data were sourced from Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) of various publications ranging from 1980 to 2020. The study used univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis. The results revealed a positive and insignificant relationship between personal income tax company's income tax (CIT), petroleum profit tax (PPT), capital gain tax (CGT), value added tax (VAT), custom excise duties (CED) and Gini coefficient for the period under study, while strong positive relationship when literacy rate moderate tax structure, and weak positive and insignificant relationship. George-Anokwuru (2023) ascertained the effect of indirect tax on inclusive growth in Nigeria from 1994-2019. To achieve the above objective, secondary data on the human development index, value-added tax, as well as customs and excise duties were sourced from the statistical bulletin of Nigeria's apex bank. Co-integration and ECM techniques were used as the main analytical tools. The regression result revealed that value-added tax has a positive and insignificant relationship with inclusive growth (human development index) in Nigeria during the period of study. At the same time, customs and excise duties have a negative and significant relationship with inclusive growth (human development index) in Nigeria during the studied period. Mamuda and Alhassan (2021) determined the effect of tax revenue on the economic growth of Nigeria. The Central Bank Statistical Bulletin was one of the secondary data sources used. A multiple regression model was employed to analyses the data collected for this study. Using GDP as an index economy, the results revealed a positive association between tax revenue and economic growth. Okoh, Edo, Akhigbodemhe and Edeoghon (2021) examined the effect of direct taxes on income redistribution in the context of Nigeria from 1990 to 2019 using annualized data set from Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) was employed to analyze the data. The results showed that personal income tax had significant positive effects on income redistribution, thus reducing income inequality in the context of Nigeria. Omes and Appah (2021) determined the effect of taxes on income inequality in Nigeria for the period 1980 to 2018. Data were collected and analyzed with univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis. The error correction mechanism revealed a significant negative effect exists

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting
<https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>, Email: contact@americaserial.com

between personal income tax, company income tax and inequality; a negative but statistically insignificant relationship exist between value added tax and income inequality; a positive but statistically insignificant relationship exist between value added tax, government spending on education, government spending on health and income inequality.

Methodology

This study utilized *Ex-Post Facto* research design. The choice of the design is based on the idea that the method provides discovery on trends and pattern of change. The study used time series data covering a period 2000 to 2023. An *ex-post facto* design is a quasi-experimental study examining how an independent variable, present in the study affects the dependent variable and in such a situation, all data will not be randomly assigned but was given equal chance.

Population and Sample Size

The Population made up of indirect tax revenues and income distribution in Nigeria.

The study selected two (2) variables among other existing variables for indirect tax revenue in Nigeria, namely; Stamp duty tax, custom and excise duty tax and Gini coefficient.

Data were extracted from federal Inland Revenue services and World Bank reports. Data extracted includes; government expenditure on goods as the dependent variable (income redistribution).

Secondary data were sourced from the financial statistical bulletin, CBN statistical bulletin as well as the Federal Inland Revenue (FIRS) for Nigeria from 2000 to 2023 using time series data based on the availability of data. The researcher collected the data into the following categories namely; Stamp duty tax, custom and excise duty tax for independent variables, while Gini coefficient represents the income redistribution.

Model Specification

This study adapted the model of Obaretin et al., (2017), whose model this study adopts. The model of Obaretin et al., (2017) is stated below:

$$GINIt = \beta_0 + \beta_1TITt + \beta_2TDTt + \beta_3OPNt + \beta_4FDIt + \beta_5INFt + \epsilon t \quad \dots 1$$

TIT = Total indirect tax revenue,

TDT= Total direct tax revenue,

FDI = Foreign direct investment,

OPN= Economic openness,

INF= Inflation rate,

GINI= Gini coefficient

The model for this study stated in its econometric form is given below:

$$GIN_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1SDT_{it} + \beta_2CED_{it} + \epsilon t \quad \dots i$$

Where:

Gini = Gini coefficient (proxied by government expenditures on infrastructural goods)

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 13 Issue 2, April-June 2025

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 8.36

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

SDT = Stamp duty tax

CED = Custom and excise duty tax,

t= Time frame,

$\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_2$ = unknown coefficients

Method of Data Analysis

This study will utilize descriptive statistics employed to summarily describe the mean, median, standard deviation, kurtosis and skewness of the study variables. Inferential statistics (regression analysis) will also be utilized with the aid of E-Views 9 using:

Panel regressions analysis: (A panel regression is a regression analysis that takes into account the relationships between each predictor variable and a single outcome variable. This type of regression is used to identify potential predictors of a particular outcome and to quantify the strength of the relationship between each predictor and the outcome) will be used in the study to compare and contrast the effect of indirect tax revenue on income distribution in Nigeria.

Decision rule

Accept the null hypothesis if the P-value is greater than 0.05 and then the alternate hypothesis will be rejected.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	LOGGINI	LOGSDT	LOGCED
Mean	4.894339	4.285275	0.855778
Median	4.790327	4.175236	0.774863
Maximum	6.547775	5.118562	2.567073
Minimum	4.347076	3.910358	0.000000
Std. Dev.	0.506267	0.333950	0.621516
Skewness	1.996333	1.818381	1.219205
Kurtosis	6.613602	4.970257	4.130065
Jarque-Bera	115.9980	68.43178	28.89155
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000001
Sum	469.8565	411.3864	82.15471
Sum Sq. Dev.	24.34912	10.59466	36.69686
Observations	96	96	96

Source: E-views 9 (2025)

Table 1, observed that the mean values of the income redistribution (LOGGINI) stood at 4.894, with standard deviation of 0.506. The maximum value is 6.548 and minimum value of 4.347. The mean value of stamp duty tax (LOGSDT) is 4.285 with standard deviation of 0.334. The maximum value is 5.119, and minimum of 3.910. Similarly, the mean values of the custom and excise duty tax

(LOGCED) revealed 0.856, WITH standard deviation of 0.622. The maximum value is 2.567, and minimum value of 0.000. The kurtosis of 6.613602, 4.970257, and 4.130065, for LOGGINI, LOGSDT and LOGCED, respectively, showing a distribution that is strong, suggesting a concentration of values around the mean with potential outliers. The Jarque-Bera probability of 0.000000, 0.000000 and 0.000001 confirms that the LOGGINI, LOGSDT and LOGCED data is significantly non-normally distributed showed that traditional parametric analyses may need to be approached with caution.

Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Ho₂: Stamp duty tax has no significant effect on income redistribution in Nigeria.

Table 2: Panel Least Square Regression analysis testing the effect between LOGSDT, and LOGGINI

Dependent Variable: LOGGINI

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 06/14/25 Time: 11:50

Sample: 2000 2023

Periods included: 24

Cross-sections included: 4

Total panel (balanced) observations: 96

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.018839	0.665938	6.034850	0.0000
LOGSDT	0.204304	0.154937	1.318631	0.1905
R-squared	0.118162	Mean dependent var	4.89433	9
Adjusted squared	0.107717	S.D. dependent var	7	0.50626
S.E. of regression	0.504310	Akaike info criterion	1.489363	
Sum squared resid	23.90690	Schwarz criterion	1.542786	
Log likelihood	69.48940	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.510957	0.38665
F-statistic	1.738788	Durbin-Watson stat	8	

Prob(F-statistic) 0.190496

Interpretation of Regression Result

In Table 2, R-squared and adjusted Squared values were (0.12) and (0.11) respectively. This indicates that the independent variable explain about 11% of the systematic variations in income redistribution (LOGINI) over the twenty four years periods (2000-2023). The adjusted R², which represents the coefficient of determinations imply that 11% of the total variation in the dependent variable (LOGGINI) is jointly explained by the explanatory variable stamp duty tax (LOGSDT). The value of adjusted R² of 11% also shows that 89% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by other factors not captured in the study model. The F- statistics value of 1.738788 with an associated Prob.>F = 0.190 indicates that the model is fit to explain the relationship expressed in the study model and further suggests that the explanatory variables are properly selected, combined and used.

Test of Autocorrelation: using Durbin-Waston (DW) statistics which we obtained from our regression result in table 2, it is observed that DW statistics is 0.387 and an Akika Info Criterion and Schwarz Criterion which are 1.489 and 1.543 respectively also further confirms that our model is well specified.

Table 2 indicates that stamp duty tax has a positive significant effect on government income redistribution in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.204304 with t-statistic of 1.319 which is positive but insignificant effect at 5% level of significance.

Since the P-value of the test was 0.190 higher than 0.05 (5%). this study upholds that stamp duty tax has no significant effect on income redistribution in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₃: Custom and Excise duty tax has no significant effect on income redistribution in Nigeria.

Table 3: Panel Least Square Regression analysis testing the effect between LOGCED and LOGGINI

Dependent Variable: LOGGINI

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 06/14/25 Time: 11:51

Sample: 2000 2023

Periods included: 24

Cross-sections included: 4

Total panel (balanced) observations: 96

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.512521	0.074212	60.80613	0.0000
LOGCED	0.446164	0.070293	6.347242	0.0000

R-squared	0.300009	Mean dependent var	4.894339
Adjusted R-squared	0.292563	S.D. dependent var	0.506267
S.E. of regression	0.425818	Akaike info criterion	1.151003
Sum squared resid	17.04416	Schwarz criterion	1.204427
Log likelihood	-53.24815	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.172598
F-statistic	40.28749	Durbin-Watson stat	0.622717
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Interpretation of Regression Result

In Table 3, R-squared and adjusted Squared values were (0.30) and (0.29) respectively. This indicates that the independent variable explain about 29% of the systematic variations in income redistribution (LOGINI) over the twenty four years periods (2000-2023). The adjusted R², which represents the coefficient of determinations imply that 29% of the total variation in the dependent variable (LOGGINI) is jointly explained by the explanatory variable custom and excise duty tax (LOGCED). The value of adjusted R² of 29% also shows that 71% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by other factors not captured in the study model. The F- statistics value of 40.28749 with an associated Prob.>F = 0.000 indicates that the model is fit to explain the relationship expressed in the study model and further suggests that the explanatory variables are properly selected, combined and used.

Test of Autocorrelation: using Durbin-Waston (DW) statistics which we obtained from our regression result in table 3, it is observed that DW statistics is 0.623 and an Akika Info Criterion and Schwarz Criterion which are 1.151 and 1.204 respectively also further confirms that our model is well specified.

Table 3 indicates that custom and excise duty tax has a positive significant effect on government income redistribution in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.446164 with t-statistic of 6.347242 which is positive and significant effect at 5% level of significance.

Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%). this study upholds that custom and excise duty tax significantly affect income redistribution in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The ascertained the effect of indirect tax revenue on income distribution in Nigeria from 2000 -2023, using value added tax, stamp duty tax and custom and excise duty tax as the independent variables. Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses, the results revealed that value added tax and custom and excise duty tax significantly affect income redistribution in Nigeria, while stamp duty tax has no significant effect on income redistribution in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommended the followings;

- i. In order to reverse the insignificant effect of stamp duty tax, government should provide the necessary enabling environment that are needed to support both domestic and foreign investment so they can attract more capital gain that will boost taxable income thereby improve in the economic growth of these countries.
- ii. Since CED has significant effect on the productivity of Nigeria, government should devise means of curbing corruption and leakages in the CED administration and continue in investing in infrastructure and public goods and services.

References

- Adam, H. (2023). Global excise tax application and trends. FISCAL FACT No. 810 Apr. 2023.
- Aondoakaa, K., Austine U. & Isaac K. (2022). An analysis of taxation and economic growth in Nigeria *UMYU Journal of Accounting and Finance Research* VOL. 3 NO. 1 June, 2022 pg. 154
- Ashiedu, I.P., Okafor, T.G., Amahalu, N.N., & Obi, J.C. (2022). Effect of tax revenue on national development of Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 8(1), 50-64.
- Appah, E. & Iweias, S. S. (2023). Taxes and income inequality in Nigeria: 1980 – 2020. *African Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* ISSN: 2689-5080 6(1), 100-128.
- Awe, A. S. & Rufus, O. O. (2012). Determinant of income distribution in the Nigeria Economy. *International Business and Management*, 5(1), 126-137.
- Edo, O. C, Okafor, A. & Justice., A, E. (2020). Corporate taxes and foreign direct investments: an impact analysis, *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 10(9), 51-62.
- Edo, O.C; Okafor, A; Emmanuel, A. (2020). Tax policy and foreign direct investment: a regime change analysis. *J. Fin. Bank. Review*, 5 (3): 84 – 98 <https://doi.org/10.35609/jfbr.2020.5.3> (3)
- Ezu, G. K., & Okoh, J. I. (2016). Effects of tax revenue on selected macroeconomic variables in Nigeria. *Journal of the Management Sciences*, 12(1), 41–58
- Edewusi, D. G. & Ajayi, I. E. (2019). The nexus between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting*, 4(2), 45-55.

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 13 Issue 2, April-June 2025

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 8.36

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- .Ezejiofor, R A., & Apete, C., 2023. Stamp Duty Tax and Growth of Economy: Evidence from Nigeria. *Macro Management & Public Policies*, 5(1): 50-56. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30564/mmpp.v5i1.5523>.
- George-Anokwuru, C. C. (2023). The effect of customs and excise duties on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom* 11(12). ISSN 2348 0386. Dec 2023 Licensed under Creative Common <https://ijecm.co.uk/>
- Ilaboya, O. J. (2013). Direct versus indirect taxation and Income inequality in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 1(1), 1-15.
- Iwegbe, E. & Daddau, H. (2024). Impact of Value Added Tax on Economic Growth of Nigeria. *UNIZIK Journal of Marketing (UJofM)*, Vol. 1(1), Sept. 2024 ISSN xxxx-xxxx. 118-130 <https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/ujofm>.
- Lustig, N. (2017). Fiscal policy, income redistribution and poverty reduction in low- and middle-income countries. Center for global development working paper, (448)
- Manukaji, I. J. (2018). Effect of tax structure on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economic Research*, 6(1), 1 – 11.
- Madzinová, R. (2017). Impact of government spending on income inequality. *Annals of the University of Oradea, Economic Science Series*, 26(2), 210-220.
- Mamuda, A. U. & Alhassan I. (2021). Tax Revenue and its Impact on the Economic Growth of Nigeria, *International Academic Journal of Management and Marketing*, 6(6), 112 – 123.
- Obaretin, O., Akhor, S. O. & Oseghale, O. E. (2017). Taxation an effective tool for income redistribution in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(4), 187-196.
- Ofoegbu, G. N., Akwu, O. D. & Oliver, O. (2016). Empirical analysis of effect of tax revenue on economic development of Nigeria. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 6(10), 604-613.
- Obadiaru, E., Brian-Kufre, O. & Adebajji, A. (2024) *The impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 5 (1). pp. 566-571. ISSN 2582-7138

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 13 Issue 2, April-June 2025

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 8.36

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Okoh F. I., Edo O.C., Akhigbodemhe E.J., & Edeoghon, I. O. (2021). Direct Taxes and Income Redistribution in Nigeria, *GATR Global J. Bus. Soc. Sci. Review*, 9(2), 182 – 196. <https://doi.org/10.35609/gjbssr>. 2021.9.2(8)

Obaretin, O., Akhor, S. O. & Oseghale, O. E. (2017). Taxation an effective tool for income redistribution in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(4), 187-196.

Omesi, I. & Appah, E. (2020). Tax structure and economic growth in Nigeria: An ARDL evidence from 1980 – 2018. *International Journal of Innovations in Marketing and Accounting Research*, 8(1), 108-124.

Okeke, M.N., Mbonu, C.M., & Amahalu, N.N. (2018b). Effect of tax revenue on economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Business, Economics and Management*, 2(4), 25-61.

Okonkwo, I. V. & Chukwu, K.O. (2019). Government tax revenue and economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Business, Economics and Management*, 3(3), 91 - 105.

Sitharaman, N. (2022). Tax revenue. <https://www.business-standard.com/about/what-is-tax-revenue>. Retrieved 25/05/2022.

The Guardian. (2019, July 30). Lingerin poverty and consequences. Taxation and income inequality in Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Economics and Marketing Research*, 4(3), 104–116.

Ugbede, J. (2020). Nigeria: extreme inequality in numbers. <https://www.oxfam.org/en/nigeria-extreme-inequality-numbers>.